

EUNOMIA's team [latest publication](#) on Cutter Business Technology Journal is trying to provide answers on how technology can be used to support our research for trustful information. Can we trust a stranger? So many posts, who can we trust?

As the online world of information enlarges, there is also an increasing demand on trustworthiness of user-generated, online-shared content. While a significant portion of social media posts have proven to be a great source of knowledge and news, other posts have purposefully spread false information.

The article includes a presentation of contemporary decentralized environments that aim at exploiting the potential of end users' representation as contributors to the credibility-checking process. What technologies would successfully support the implementation of a human-centric solution, to assist social media users in gauging the trustworthiness of information, in a complementary way to the usual practice of "information hygiene" guidelines?

In contrast to centralized platforms, where the data of vast numbers of users is held by, and in some cases subject to the censorship of, a very small number of social network providers, decentralized online social networks are based on distributed information management schemes, empowered by trusted servers or peer-to-peer (P2P) systems.

A new approach, however, involves the user in the process, exploiting the potential of crowdsourcing. In this direction, the research project [EUNOMIA](#) addresses the challenges of misinformation in social media, by actively encouraging citizen participation in content verification by voting on content trustworthiness. The focus is on the users to take ownership of the problem of disinformation, in contrast to the existing technologies used such as third-party fact-checkers or computer software.

The full article can be found here: <https://www.cutter.com/article/how-trust-stranger>